

An Examination of Physical Education Teachers' Views on Professionalism in the Teaching Profession

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Abstract

This study aims to examine physical education teachers' views on professionalism in the teaching profession. The research consists of 10 physical education teachers working within the Gaziantep Provincial Directorate of National Education. In this study, the face-to-face interview technique was used in accordance with the principle of complete voluntariness. Using the interview technique, one of the qualitative research methods, the data obtained were analyzed using content analysis. The results of the research revealed that physical education teachers emphasized that professionalism requires good management of the process, love for the profession, and hard work. At the same time, it was determined that a professional teacher should be experienced in their field, success-oriented, and value different opinions. Furthermore, the physical education teachers who participated in the study stated that they generally viewed the teaching profession as professional, but did not consider themselves professional in their field and expressed that they had some shortcomings. It was also observed that certain situations at school affected the teachers' professionalism, while it was concluded that teaching knowledge, subject knowledge, and training knowledge were sufficient for teacher professionalism.

Keywords: Physical education, Teacher, Profession, Professionalism.

INTRODUCTION

In order to meet the high academic standards and high-quality expectations required of them, teachers are expected to update and develop their knowledge, skills, and abilities through professional development (Craft, 2002; Baştürk, 2012; Özdemir, 2016). Teachers are encouraged to work collaboratively, form learning communities, cooperate with parents, and specialize in order to adapt to this development process (Hargreaves, 2000). The teaching profession has undergone intellectual transformations over time and continues to exist as a professional occupation today. This situation makes it important for teachers to demonstrate professional behavior in their professional practices. Like any profession, the teaching profession has its own unique characteristics. It can be said that these characteristics actually define the profession. Professions become professional as they change and develop these characteristics. The teaching profession has been part of the professionalization movement through reforms made throughout history (Anderson, 2012). This situation demonstrates that the teaching profession has developed its characteristic features over time in order to become professionalized and has evolved alongside the concept of the school. The fact that teachers receive pre-service training, that there are criteria and processes for appointments, that the profession is divided into various branches, that standards have been developed for practice, and that teachers earn money in return for their work can be considered characteristics of the teaching profession becoming or being in the process of becoming professionalized. Along with these characteristics of the profession, educational organizations continue to develop in today's changing and evolving conditions. As the teaching profession continues to develop, the quality of the work performed becomes important. The quality of the work is also related to the internal motivation and internal control of the people doing the work, their desires and curiosity. These indicators can also be referred to as individual professionalism. Teachers develop their organizational professionalism through the characteristic features of their profession, while they develop their individual professionalism through the successes they demonstrate in the educational process. The replacement of individual professionalism with organizational professionalism also constitutes professional expertise (Evets, 2011; Altınkurt and Yılmaz, 2014). Professionalism can be defined as the attitudes and behaviors of the employee towards their own work (Kılınç et al., 2015). Evans (2008) examines teacher professionalism in three dimensions: behavior, attitude, and intellectuality. The behavioral dimension depends on the degree to which teachers fulfill the requirements of the profession. The dimension of attitude refers to a teacher's perspective and perception of the profession. The dimension of intellectualism encompasses teachers possessing the knowledge and skills required by the profession, continuously developing themselves, mastering their field, and closely following developments in the field. Day (2002) addresses teacher professionalism in terms of creating effective teaching practices, creating an environment conducive to learning, and developing professional knowledge and skills to provide students with richer learning experiences. Therefore, Day (2002) emphasizes professional development more in the context of professionalism. The concept of professional professionalism is defined in different ways by various researchers. Yılmaz and Altınkurt (2014) define it as an internal factor that directs the individual to pursue their own learning and reflects their desires and curiosity. According to another definition, teacher professionalization is a focus that reflects the development and

improvement of teaching carried out in the classroom (Tschannen Moran, 2009). From the perspective of teachers, professional expertise can be described as skills such as improving one's knowledge of the profession, being knowledgeable about events occurring at school, and being able to assist students according to their needs (Girgin, Çetingöz, & Ekinçi-Vural, 2009). In light of the definitions provided, professional teachers are expected to take responsibility for facilitating student learning (Timperley, 2008), carry out activities to organize the teaching environment in the classroom, implement practices that will achieve effective teaching as stakeholders who fulfill the school's objectives, evaluate whether the practices implemented are effective, and thus develop emotional attachment to the school (Tschannen Moran, 2009).

Teachers' professional expertise can be defined as internalized beliefs regarding the attitudes, interactions, and behaviors they exhibit in school settings to improve student achievement (Yılmaz and Altınkurt, 2015). Evetts (2011) explains professionalism as a professional value. What Evetts refers to as a value system are professional ethical values. Teachers' professional ethical values are key behaviors of professionalism. Teachers construct their discourse based on values in their relationships with students. These values and practices constitute teachers' autonomy (Hargreaves, 1994, pp. 434-435). Evetts (2011, p. 411) explains professional professionalism through ethical principles, cooperation, strong unity of purpose, evaluation-decision making, trust, values, and autonomy. Evans (2008) evaluates teachers' professional professionalism within professional development and explains professional development as functional development and attitude development. Functional development is defined as the improvement of teachers' performance, while attitudinal development is defined as the process of changing teachers' attitudes towards their work.

Professionalism is of great importance in the teaching profession, as it is in all professions. In many professions, professionalism can be seen as important in terms of individuals' professional development, contributing to their careers, and, of course, contributing to the professional group they belong to and the institutions they work for. However, professionalism has a special importance in the teaching profession. Teachers' professionalism is directly related to their ability to better understand student needs in the classroom, provide appropriate learning environments for students, and effectively determine educational strategies. Based on this, this study aims to examine physical education teachers' views on professionalism in the teaching profession. To this end, answers were sought to the following questions:

1. What are your thoughts on professionalism?
2. What makes a professional teacher?
3. Do you view teaching as a professional occupation?
4. What are your thoughts on the professionalism of physical education teachers?
5. What factors influence professionalism in the teaching profession?
6. Is subject knowledge and pedagogical training sufficient for professionalism in the teaching profession?

METHOD

Research Model

The interview technique, one of the qualitative research methods, was used in the study. Qualitative research is a method that offers researchers greater flexibility compared to quantitative research, providing different approaches to data collection, analysis, and research design (Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2006). Qualitative research is defined as research that uses qualitative data collection methods such as observation, interviews, and document analysis, and follows a qualitative process aimed at presenting perceptions and events in a realistic and holistic manner in their natural environment. Qualitative research is an approach that prioritizes researching and understanding social phenomena within their context, based on a theory-building approach (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). The research design is the phenomenology design from qualitative research designs. The phenomenology design focuses on phenomena that we are aware of but do not have a deep and detailed understanding of. The interview method was used to obtain more detailed and in-depth information about physical education teachers' views on professionalism in the teaching profession, their approaches, and their comments on the definition. Through interviews, which are a systematic data collection process determined by a research design, unobservable phenomena such as experiences, attitudes, thoughts, intentions, comments, mental perceptions, and reactions are sought to be understood (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). The interview method is designed to obtain the same type of information from different people by focusing on similar topics (Patton, 1987:111; cited in Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013).

Research Group

The study examined physical education teachers' views on professionalism in the teaching profession. For this purpose, the study group consisted of physical education teachers working in schools affiliated with the Gaziantep Provincial Directorate of National Education. In selecting the working group, maximum diversity sampling, one of the purposeful sampling methods, was used. According to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2013), the aim is to create a relatively small sample and to reflect the diversity of individuals who may be involved in the problem being studied to the maximum extent. The purpose of creating a sample based on maximum diversity is to try to find any common or shared phenomena among diverse situations in order to make generalizations and to reveal the different dimensions of the problem according to this diversity (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013:137). The number of physical education teachers in the sample group for this study was set at 10. Data related to the research group are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Personal Characteristics of the Research Group

Variables	Groups	n	%
Gender	Male	6	60
	Female	4	40
Marital Status	Married	8	80
	Single	2	20
School Level of Assignment	High School	6	60
	Middle School	4	40
Years of Professional Experience	1-5 Years	3	30
	6-10 Years	2	20
	11-15 Years	2	20
	16-20 Years	2	20
	20 Years and above	1	10

N=10

Preparation and Implementation of the Open-Ended Question Form

A semi-structured interview form consisting of 6 items was used to collect qualitative data in the research. Through the interview technique, which is frequently used in qualitative research, the researcher attempts to understand unobservable situations such as attitudes, experiences, intentions, thoughts, mental perceptions, interpretations, and reactions (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). A comprehensive literature review was conducted to prepare the interview form. When preparing the semi-structured interview form used as a data collection tool, the researcher first conducted a field survey and created a pool of questions for the semi-structured interview form that could be asked to physical education teachers on the subject. Subsequently, the questions developed with the assistance of three experts were reviewed, and the semi-structured interview form was finalized. None of the participants included in the study were coerced into participating in the research, and the principle of confidentiality was strictly adhered to during the administration and collection of the questionnaires. In the study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 volunteer physical education teachers working in schools affiliated with the Gaziantep Provincial Directorate of National Education. The interviews were recorded using a voice recorder and later transcribed.

Data Analysis

Write the analysis methods applied in the study here.

The data obtained from the interview form used in the study were recorded using a voice recorder. After the application, the qualitative data in the voice recordings containing the responses of school administrators were transferred to a computer by the researcher. The qualitative data were then analyzed using content analysis. The content analysis technique, frequently used in the analysis of data obtained from the questions in the interview form, was utilized. The aim is to arrive at concepts that can explain the collected data (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013).

The steps followed are as follows:

- ❖ Collection of research data
- ❖ Coding of data
- ❖ Creation of themes
- ❖ Organization of data according to codes and themes
- ❖ Interpretation of findings

Ethical Statement

This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from all participants who voluntarily agreed to take part in the research.

RESULTS

This section presents findings based on data obtained from interviews conducted with the working group. Direct quotations from the interviews are provided, with the participant number from the participant list added before each quotation to indicate which participant made the statement.

Table 2. Distribution of participants' views on what they think about professionalism.

Themes	n	%
Managing the process well	5	29.5
Loving your profession and your work	4	23.6
Working hard	3	17.6
Working with discipline	3	17.6
Being aware of your potential	2	11.7
Total	17	100

Table 2 examines participants' views on professionalism. 29.5% stated that it is necessary to manage the process well, while 23.6% stated that it is necessary to love one's profession and work. At the same time, 17.6% of participants stated that it is necessary to work hard and be disciplined, while 2 teachers stated that it is necessary to be aware of one's potential.

Table 3. Distribution of participants' views on what a professional teacher should be like.

Themes	n	%
Must be an expert and skilled in their field	6	31.5
Must be intelligent	5	26.3
Must be success-oriented	4	21.1
Must value different opinions	4	21.1
Total	19	100

Table 3 examines participants' views on what makes a professional teacher. Thirty-one point five percent stated that a professional teacher should be an expert and master in their field. Additionally, 26.3% of participating teachers stated that a professional teacher should be intelligent, while 21.1% stated that a professional teacher should be success-oriented and value different opinions.

Table 4. Distribution of participants' views on whether they consider the teaching profession to be professional.

Themes	N	%
I see it professionally	7	70
I don't see it professionally	2	20
I see it as a fee	1	10
Total	10	100

Table 4 examines participants' views on whether they consider the teaching profession to be professional. The majority, 70%, stated that they consider it professional, while 20% stated that they do not consider it professional. One teacher participating in the study stated that they consider the teaching profession to be a job for pay.

Table 5. Distribution of participants' views on their own professionalism.

Themes	N	%
I am not sufficiently qualified professionally	5	50
I am sufficiently qualified professionally	3	30
In-service training should be provided	2	20
Total	10	100

Table 5 examines participants' views on their own professionalism. Half of the participants stated that they did not consider themselves professional, while 30% stated that they considered themselves adequate. In addition, two teachers expressed the view that training was necessary.

Table 6. Distribution of participants' views on the factors affecting professionalism in the teaching profession.

Themes	N	%
Positive and negative situations at school	5	50
Administrators	3	30
No opinion	2	20
Total	10	100

Table 6 examines participants' views on the factors affecting professionalism in the teaching profession. Fifty percent stated that positive and negative situations at school have an impact. Additionally, 30% of the teachers participating in the study stated that administrators have an impact, while 20% stated that they had no opinion.

Table 7. Distribution of participants' views on whether their teaching professional knowledge, subject knowledge, and training knowledge are sufficient for professionalism.

Themes	N	%
Sufficient	7	70

Not sufficient	3	30
Total	10	100

Table 7 shows the participants' views on whether their teaching knowledge, subject knowledge, and training knowledge are sufficient for professionalism. While 70% stated that they are sufficient, 30% expressed the view that they are not sufficient.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This section of the study presents the findings and conclusions based on the results obtained in order to examine physical education teachers' views on professionalism in the teaching profession. When examining participants' views on professionalism, it became clear that managing the process well and loving one's profession and work are paramount. In addition, participants stated that professionalism requires working hard, working diligently, and being aware of one's potential. Based on the participants' views, we can say that the concept of professionalism requires being competent in one's field and taking ownership of one's profession. Reviewing the literature, Gencer (2023) in his study titled "Professionalization and Teaching," identified professionalism as expertise, qualified education, professional socialization, ethical standards, scientific methods and openness to innovation, professional commitment and identification with the profession, experience, the existence of a reward system, social status, autonomy, and the existence of professional organizations (Gencer, 2023). When examining participants' views on what constitutes a professional teacher, the majority stated that a professional teacher should be an expert and master in their field. In addition, physical education teachers participating in the study indicated that a professional teacher should be intelligent, success-oriented, and value different opinions. Therefore, it can be said that a professional teacher should be well-equipped in their field and have foresight. In a study conducted by Uzun and colleagues (2023), a professional teacher was described as understanding, empathetic, valuing people, open to criticism and change, and a contemporary individual (Uzun et al., 2023). In a study conducted by Özbay, emphasis is placed on the need for teachers to be problem-solving experts in general, socially and humanely minded, open to change, and possess advanced communication skills (Özbay, 2001).

When examining participants' views on whether they perceive teaching as a professional occupation, it is evident that the majority view teaching as a professional occupation. However, it has been determined that some participants do not view teaching as a professional occupation and instead see it as a means of earning a salary. Based on this, we can say that teaching is a sacred profession and should be valued. In this sense, it can be said that it is necessary to make society feel that the teaching profession is valuable.

When examining participants' views on their own professionalism, it is observed that they do not express themselves as professionals, while some consider themselves professionally competent. Based on this, we can conclude that in-service training is necessary regarding both professional competence and teacher professionalism. When reviewing the literature, in the study by Çekin (2015), teachers state that they possess professional competencies. In the research conducted by Bayhan (2011) and Cerit (2012), teachers' levels of professional expertise were found to be low. The results of many studies examining teachers' professional

professionalism have concluded that teachers see themselves as professionals (Altinkurt and Yılmaz, 2014; Çelik and Yılmaz, 2015).

When examining participants' views on the factors affecting professionalism in the teaching profession, it was observed that both positive and negative situations at school had an impact. Some teachers stated that administrators affected their professionalism. Based on this, we can say that negative situations affecting teachers' professionalism should be identified and addressed through targeted efforts. In a study on this topic, it was stated that in order to remove the obstacles to teachers' professional and personal development, the existing status coach structure should be changed and the number of more qualified, purposeful in-service training and seminars should be increased (Yırcı, 2017). Similarly, in Çekin's (2015) study, teachers believe that personality, school management, and policies are effective in their professional careers. When evaluated in the context of these studies, it is seen that current education policies, school practices, and bureaucratic procedures are obstacles to both professionalization and teachers' personal and professional development. When examining the participants' views on whether their teaching knowledge, subject knowledge, and training knowledge were sufficient for professionalism, it was found that the vast majority expressed the view that they were sufficient, while some expressed the view that they were insufficient.

As a result, it has been highlighted that physical education teachers need to manage the process well, love their profession, and work hard in order to be professional. At the same time, it has been determined that a professional teacher should be experienced in their field, success-oriented, and value different opinions. Furthermore, the physical education teachers who participated in the study stated that they generally view the teaching profession as professional, but they do not see themselves as professional in their field and feel they have some shortcomings. It was also observed that certain situations at school affect teachers' professionalism, while it was concluded that teaching knowledge, subject knowledge, and training knowledge are sufficient for teacher professionalism.

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